

**METHODOLOGY FOR SUPPORTING NEP 2020 BY IDENTIFYING GAPS IN
INDIVIDUAL LEARNER POTENTIAL WITH REFERENCE TO PEERS USING
STATISTICAL MEANS VARIANCE AND CORRELATION**

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Abstract

NEP 2020 project aims to improve India's educational system by recognizing and nurturing student strength. This study presents a methodology to support each learner's individual potential through statistical analysis of baseline assessment and formative project-based learning. Mean and variance are used to determine a student's level, and Correlations between parameters and overall score assign weight to activities for holistic development.

It was observed that students A2, A7 and A10 had a high holistic index of 4, while A1, A3 and A5 had a less holistic index of 2. The mean and variance of Mental, Physical, Social, Spiritual, Integrity, and Subject Aptitude are 2.71, 3.48, 3.06, 3.4, 3.16, 3.76 and 1.18, 1.39, 1.36, 1.51, 1.51, 1.65 respectively. Statistical analysis showed a correlation between assessment parameters and the holistic index of 100 students. The results of the assessment of A1 are Subject, Mental, Physical, Social, Spiritual and Integrity aptitude as 2,2,3,2,1 and 4. Holistic Index for A1 is 2. A1 is classified as below average learner and the holistic index is highly correlated to mental, spiritual and social aptitude. Thus, assigning project-based learning activities on enhancing mental, social and spiritual aptitude may help to improve individual learner potential. To improve holistic potential of A1, project-based learning activities based on mental, spiritual and social aptitude is assigned. The results of desired level assessment show improvement were noticed in students in the holistic index for A1 is 4 and A6 is 3. This validates the efficiency of the proposed methodology to improve individual learner potential, which will help galvanize NEP 2020 in the higher education system.

Keywords: NEP 2020, Baseline Assessment, Desired level Assessment, Holistic index, AICTEE PARAKH, Project based learning.

1) Introduction:

Due to its emphasis on ensuring that everyone has access to a high-quality education, the Indian educational system is significant from the standpoint of national development. The NEP 2020 project aims to improve India's educational standards. NEP places a strong emphasis on student diversity and a wide education. It is essential to recognize, pinpoint, and build on each student's particular abilities as part of NEP 2020. The evaluation of students' cognitive abilities, which is crucial for their overall growth, is not taken into account by the traditional exam system in Indian education [1-3].

Assessment is the bridge between teaching and learning. Assessment can drive improvement, shape behaviours and maximise student learning. ("Five basics of baseline assessment - CEM") It makes the learning visible and important for a faculty to drive their cohort. PARAKH caters to both – synchronous and asynchronous assessments wherein the whole institution, and /or the student can themselves take the test to self-assess their knowledge as compared to their peers. The goal of the PARAKH is to 'a) produce skilled graduates by attaining Academic Skills and Higher Order Thinking Skills b) Skilled Graduates can contribute towards productivity and innovation, which will lead to higher economic growth. c) To Fill up the gap between Passed and Placed Students in AICTE Approved Institutions [4-7].

Following this study, AICTE PARAKH will evaluate how far the academic, social, cognitive, and physical development of the pupils has advanced. The approach presented in this study makes use of statistical analysis of the AICTE PARAKH and provides a method for maximizing individual potential. This study investigates the statistical methodology for galvanizing NEP 2020 by supporting each learner's individual potential through statistical analysis of AICTE PARAKH assessment by demonstrating case studies and desired level assessment through project-based learning[8-11].

II) The need to comprehend each learner's potential from the perspective of NEP 2020:

NEP aims to upgrade India's education to global standards, which it will achieve by fostering the unique capabilities of individuals and encouraging holistic development. The education system aims toward sustainable development of learners which can be achieved through holistic development. The current assessment of the Indian education system doesn't give a clear picture of students' holistic index. It primarily focuses on subject aptitude. Hence there is a need to assess students to find their individual potential and holistic index to support NEP 2020. AICTE PARAKH evaluation system covers a baseline assessment to understand individual learners' potential academically, socially, cognitively, and physically. aptitudes of students. It also gives an overall rating which can be considered a holistic index of students. Statistical tools can be applied to the assessment of AICTE PARAKH of students to understand individual potential with reference to peers [12-14].

The National Education Policy states 'it is essential that an identified set of skills and values are incorporated at each stage of learning' for the holistic development of learners.' Holistic Development in a student fuels the attainment of the 21st Century Skills as a student profile over the larger perspective. With Higher Education Institutions focusing on research-driven academia, building student profiles through active assessments helps in the overlay of achieving the Holistic development parameters[14-16]. The Industrial Revolution is dynamically changing, there are many perceptions, and renowned traits which are expected out of the student post their graduation. Andragogical learning traits and methods have to be revamped in order to create lifelong learners, not only through formal education but also through social and creating self-learning efficacy amongst the students [17-20].

III) Data collection

Data collection is done twice to achieve the holistic development of students. First data collection is done to do a baseline assessment of students before the start of the semester. For baseline assessment, AICTE PARAKH is used. Second data collection is done to do a desired level assessment at the mid and end of the semester. For desired level assessment formative project-based learning is used.

IV) Methodology:

The methodology for supporting each learner's individual potential through statistical analysis of baseline AICTE PARAKH assessment and desired level assessment through formative project-based learning assessment. Figure 1 represents the methodology for supporting individual potential.

Figure 1: Methodology for supporting holistic baseline assessment

1) Individual learner Holistic Baseline Assessment:

Data collection of AICTE PARAKH is done program-wise. To understand the potential of each learner level we have to observe the AICTE PARAKH assessment of an individual student with reference to peers. To observe individual potential with reference to peers we need to statistical tools mean, variance and correlation. After comparing individual learner potential with reference to mean assessment we can understand the level of learner potential. The difficulty of mentors understanding individual learners' potential such as holistic index varies according to the variance within the parameters of assessment. For example, the spiritual level of students has more variance than the

mental aptitude. Hence weightage of spiritual assessment is less than the mental assessment in order to understand individual learner potential. For the holistic development of learners, it is very important to create the right balance for students' social, emotional, psychological, physical, and intellectual aspects. Many aspects of a learner's potential—social, emotional, psychological, physical, and intellectual—are observed. Correlation of various aspects is found with a holistic index. For example, if mental aptitude is highly correlated to the holistic index then improving mental aptitude activities can be given more weightage. Supporting each learner's individual potential through statistical analysis of the AICTE PARAKH assessment. Figure 2 represent the AICTE PARAKH baseline assessment for assessing individual learner holistic potential.

Figure 2: Individual learner baseline assessment

In this paper, we have used AICTE PARAKH as the baseline assessment and project-based learning as desired level assessment. The AICTE PARAKH assessment is assessing students' individual learners' potential academically, socially, cognitively, and physically. The overall score can be considered a holistic index of the students. The student's assessment is compared with their peers to understand the benchmark. Based on the analysis students are recommended and assisted to work where they are lacking to achieve a holistic index. Project-based learning continuous evaluation is used to track whether students are progressing in the right direction. Then to check whether students have achieved the desired level of project-based learning end semester evaluation is done.

2) Gap Analysis to understand learners' individual potential by using statistical analysis with reference to peers:

Understanding individual learners' potential with reference to peers is very much important. Peers play a major role in enhancing individual learner potential. Peer gives an environment for the individual to develop holistically. [Paper] Hence understanding individual learner aptitude with reference to peers is essential to do a gap analysis of individual learner potential with reference to peers. The proposed methodology for gap analysis is shown in figure 3

Figure 3: Proposed methodology for gap Analysis to understand learners' individual potential by using statistical analysis with reference to peer

3) Mentoring of individual learners based on gap analysis:

Gap analysis of individual learner potential in all assessment parameters for holistic index with reference to peer is done. For determining a student's level as being average, above average, or poor, the mean and variance of all the students in the program are considered as a benchmark. The second statistical study is based on AICTE PAAKH which looks for correlations between different parameters and the overall score provided by the AICTE PARAKH, which represents the student's holistic index. The correlation between the holistic index and assessment parameter is identified. Activities are given to students according to development based on the assessment parameter and correlation index. The Assignment of activities based on project-based learning gives more weightage assessment parameters which have more correlation with the holistic index. Hence, in relation to their peers, the statistical metrics of mean and variance aid in understanding each student's potential. The second statistical study of the link between the evaluation parameter and the holistic index would make assigning weight to activities for holistic development easier.

4) Desired level assessment:

The desired level assessment is done based on project-based learning. Figure 4 represents the flow chart for desired level assessment. The AICTE PARAKH holistic assessment parameters are mapped with parameters of project-based learning which are evaluated by a guide. The subject aptitude is mapped with the ability to do a literature survey. Mental aptitude is mapped with the ability to draw inferences through experiments and solutions. Spiritual aptitude is mapped with collaborative problem-solving ability. Physical aptitude is mapped with individual stamina to solve complex problems. Social aptitude to solve interpersonal skills at work. Integrity aptitude is the ability to follow academic integrity.

Figure 4: Desired level project base assessment

V) Results and Discussion:

1) Results of statistical analysis of baseline assessment:

Table 1 shows the AICTE PARAKH assessment of students. Students A1, A3, A4 and A5 have the highest holistic index. Student A7 has a very less holistic index. Thus A7 and A2 need to be mentored with reference to peers based on the assessment parameter. To understand A7 potential with reference to peer assessment parameters can be compared with the mean and variance of class and then mentored for holistic development

Student	Subject Aptitude	Mental Aptitude	Physical aptitude	Social aptitude	Spiritual aptitude	Integrity aptitude	Holistic Index (Overall rating)
A1	2	2	3	2	1	4	2
A2	5	4	3	3	4	4	4
A3	5	2	3	2	2	5	3
A4	3	2	3	2	4	2	3
A5	4	4	3	5	3	4	4
A6	2	3	3	2	5	2	2
A7	5	2	5	3	2	2	2
A8	5	2	2	4	3	5	3
A9	5	3	2	2	2	2	3
A10	5	4	2	4	3	4	4

Table 1: AICTE PARAKH assessment for students

It can be observed from the table that the highest mean and lowest variance are obtained for subject aptitude. The mean value of high with low variance for subject aptitude shows that the mean value majority of students have similar high aptitude in the subject. Since variance is a low subject meant the value of 3.76 can be considered as standard for deciding the individual learner potential with reference to peers. Lowest in spiritual aptitude. The lowest mean and variance was observed for mental aptitude. The mean value low with reference to other assessment parameters indicates that the mental aptitude of computer program students is less and training for the entire class is required to increase the mental aptitude. The mean value low with low variance for mental aptitude indicates that mental aptitude can be considered as standard for finding individual learners' potential with reference to peers. The other parameters Physical and spiritual have a mean high and variance low

hence can be considered as a reference for understanding individual learner potential with reference to peers. The overall observation from the statistical parameter can be concluded that more weightage for training must be given to increase the mental aptitude of students which will result in an increase in the holistic index of class.

Sr.No	Assessment Parameter	Variance	Statistical Parameters for Mean 100 students	Number of students above average	A number of students have Average aptitude	Number of students below average
1	Mental Aptitude	1.18	2.71	15	15	70
2	Physical Aptitude	1.39	3.48	10	45	45
3	Social Aptitude	1.36	3.06	20	25	55
4	Spiritual Aptitude	1.51	3.40	20	20	60
5	Integrity Aptitude	1.51	3.16	35	10	55
6	Subject aptitude	1.65	3.67	70	10	20
7	Holistic Index	1.40	3.76	15	35	50

Table 2: Statistical analysis of Baseline assessment for 100 students

2) Mentoring based on results of statistical analysis:

Table 3 shows the correlation of assessment parameters with reference to a holistic index. For computer engineering programs it can be observed that the holistic index has the highest correlation with mental aptitude. As observed earlier table 2, mean for mental aptitude is also low and hence more training is required for mental aptitude. The Holistic index has the least correlation with physical aptitude and integrity aptitude. Hence least training is required for physical and integrity aptitude.

	Mental aptitude	Physical aptitude	Social aptitude	Spiritual aptitude	Integrity aptitude	Subject Aptitude
Computer Engineering	0.45	-0.12	0.36	0.46	-0.034	0.19
Civil Engineering	0.55	0.13	0.56	0.29	0.22	0.16

Table 3: Correlation of baseline assessment parameter with holistic index.

We need to enhance individual learner potential. For this suppose we observe student A1 from table 1. A1 has mental aptitude as 2, physical aptitude as 2, social aptitude as 1, spiritual aptitude as 1, integrity aptitude as 1 and subject aptitude as 1. If we have to enhance A1 learner potential, then we have to compare this A1 assessment with reference to mean values of assessment for computer programs. This will help to understand A1's potential with reference to peers. Now the mentor has to assign activity to A1 for all assessment parameters. But the mentor has to give more weightage to assessment parameters which have the highest correlation to the holistic index. This can be easily found in Table 3.

If we see the correlation from Table 3, the Holistic index is highly correlated to mental, spiritual and social aptitude. If for the computer program we observe mean values from table 2 are mental aptitude as 2.71. A1 has low values in mental and social aptitude as compared to mean values of assessment of computer programs. Thus project-based learning activities such as inference analysis and collaborative activities can be given to A1.

3) Results of desired level assessment:

Table 4 represents the desired level assessment for 100 students. The result of desired level assessment for A1 is 4. Thus, A1 has shown significant improvement in the holistic index. Similarly, improvement was noticed in students in holistic index A6 from 2 (baseline assessment) to 3 (Desired level assessment). Since no improvement was found in A7, the student was referred to a counsellor. If we compare the results of base level assessment and desired level assessment there is a significant improvement in mean and correlation values. This validated the efficiency of the proposed methodology. Thus, we can infer from the results that the proposed methodology helps in improving individual learner potential. Since the method aids in improving individual learner potential, this will result in galvanizing NEP 2020 in the higher education system.

Student	Subject Aptitude	Mental Aptitude	Physical aptitude	Social aptitude	Spiritual aptitude	Integrity aptitude	Holistic Index (Overall rating)
A1	2	2	3	2	1	4	2
A2	5	4	3	3	4	4	4
A3	5	2	3	2	2	5	3
A4	3	2	3	2	4	2	3
A5	4	4	3	5	3	4	4
A6	2	3	3	2	5	2	2
A7	5	2	5	3	2	2	2
A8	5	2	2	4	3	5	3
A9	5	3	2	2	2	2	3
A10	5	4	2	4	3	4	4

Table 4: Desired level assessment of the students

VII) Conclusion:

The traditional exam system in Indian education does not accurately assess the cognitive levels of students and evaluation of cognitive levels is essential for holistic development. Hence paper proposes a statistical analysis based methodology using baseline and formative assessment to enhance individual learner potential. The AICTE PARAKH is used to assess how students have grown academically, socially, cognitively, critically, and behaviourally, and will be used by institutions and professors to mentor students for holistic development. Formative assessments using project-based learning is used to determine if a person's potential has reached the desired level. A1 is categorised as being less lean than typical and given tasks to enhance their cerebral, social, and spiritual abilities. The outcome of the evaluation for the desired level A1 and A6 holistic index has improved significantly. This suggests that the proposed methodology serves to maximise each learner's potential and will help the higher education system move towards NEP 2020.

References

1. Verma, Dr & Kumar, Adarsh. (2021). New Education Policy 2020 of India: A Theoretical Analysis. International Journal of Business and Management Research. 9. 302-306. 10.37391/IJBMR.090308.
2. Bhaskar reddy, Vijay & Bhujanga Rao, Dr Patcha & Keerthi, G. (2023). issues and emerging challenges for nep 2020. interantional journal of scientific research in engineering and management 07. 10.55041/IJSREM20290. alok kumar”new education policy (nep) 2020: a roadmap for india 2.0 advances in global education and research” 2021 volume 4. anahei publishing. <https://doi.org/10.5038/9781955833042>
3. Aithal, Sreeramana & Aithal, Shubhrajyotsna. (2020)” Analysis of the Indian National Education Policy 2020 towards Achieving its Objectives” 2020 Vol.5. 19-41. 10.5281/zenodo.3988767.

4. A. K. Pandey, S. Kumar, B. Rajendran and B. B S, "E-Parakh: Unsupervised Online Examination System," *2020 II region 10 conference (tencon)*, Osaka, Japan, 2020, pp. 667-671, doi: 10.1109/TENCON50793.2020.9293792
5. O. Jerez, N. Baloian and G. Zurita, "Authentic Assesment Between Peers in Online Courses with a Large Number of Students," 2017 IEEE 17th International Conference on Advanced Learning Technologies (ICALT), Timisoara, Romania, 2017, pp. 235-237, doi: 10.1109/ICALT.2017.160.
6. O. Berestneva, O. Marukhina and I. Dubinina, "Intellectual Competencies Assessment in Scientific Research and Engineering Business," 2018 9th International Conference on Information, Intelligence, Systems and Applications (IISA), Zakynthos, Greece, 2018, pp. 1-7, doi: 10.1109/IISA.2018.8633602.
7. P. A. Sanger and J. Ziyatdinova, "Project based learning: Real world experiential projects creating the 21st century engineer," 2014 International Conference on Interactive Collaborative Learning (ICL), Dubai, United Arab Emirates, 2014, pp. 541-544, doi: 10.1109/ICL.2014.7017830.
8. S. A. Geertshuis, A. Bristol, M. E. A. Holmes, D. M. Clancy and S. Sambrook, "Learning and business: supporting lifelong learning and the knowledge worker through the design of quality learning systems," *Proceedings International Workshop on Advanced Learning Technologies. IWALT 2000. Advanced Learning Technology: Design and Development Issues*, Palmerston North, New Zealand, 2000, pp. 186-187, doi: 10.1109/IWALT.2000.890604.
9. J. Straub, S. Kerlin and D. Whalen, "Teaching software project management using project based learning (PBL) and group projects," 2017 IEEE International Conference on Electro Information Technology (EIT), Lincoln, NE, USA, 2017, pp. 016-021, doi: 10.1109/EIT.2017.8053323.
10. R. Bierwolf, "Project excellence or failure? Doing is the best kind of learning," in *IEEE Engineering Management Review*, vol. 44, no. 2, pp. 26-32, Second Quarter 2016, doi: 10.1109/EMR.2016.2568745.
11. T. V. Reddy, S. Kamesh, M. P. Prathap and K. Ravichand, "Holistic Assessment Methodology for Undergraduate Projects," 2016 IEEE 4th International Conference on MOOCs, Innovation and Technology in Education (MITE), Madurai, India, 2016, pp. 235-240, doi: 10.1109/MITE.2016.054.
12. Kartika Arum Sari, Zuhdan Kun Prasetyo, Widodo Setiyo Wibowo "Development of science student worksheet based on project based learning model to improve collaboration and communication skill" in *Journal of Science Education Research*, published October 2017 DOI 10.21831/jser.v1i1.16178 Dimensions ID pub.1107090925
13. Eko Putro Widoyoko. (2014). *Assessment of learning outcomes in school..* Yogyakarta: Student Library.
14. Borich, G.D. (2003). *Observation for Effective Teaching: Reaching-Based Practice*. Seventh Edition. New York: M M Publishing Company
15. Yuni Wibowo, Suratsih, & Asri Widowati. (2015). Increase in the ability of the Students in designing the curriculum through the implementation of Project Based Learning. *Mathematics and Science Education Journal*, 3 (1), 49-58.
16. Williams, S., & Hin, L. C. (2015). *Holistic Assessment: Creating Assessment with Students*. In *Taylor's 7th Teaching and Learning Conference 2014 Proceedings* (pp. 389–397). Springer Singapore. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-981-287-399-6_36
17. J. E. Kasser, "Applying Holistic Thinking to the Problem of Determining the Future Availability of Technology," in *IEEE Transactions on Systems, Man, and Cybernetics: Systems*, vol. 46, no. 3, pp. 440-444, March 2016, doi: 10.1109/TSMC.2015.2438780.
18. I. Rida, N. A. Maadeed and S. A. Maadeed, "A Novel Efficient Classwise Sparse and Collaborative Representation for Holistic Palmprint Recognition," 2018 NASA/ESA Conference on Adaptive Hardware and Systems (AHS), Edinburgh, UK, 2018, pp. 156-161, doi: 10.1109/AHS.2018.8541428.
19. E. V. Volkova, V. M. Rusalov and M. N. Nilopets, "An expert system for evaluation of human mental resources: Holistic and developmental approach," 2017 Intelligent Systems Conference (IntelliSys), London, UK, 2017, pp. 527-530, doi: 10.1109/IntelliSys.2017.8324345.